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Bio-utilization of fruits waste

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Introduction: The process of collecting, treating and disposal of solid wastes is termed as Solid waste Management (SWM). Solid wastes are classified as Municipal Solid waste (MSW), hazardous wastes, industrial wastes, agricultural wastes and bio-medical wastes. In Tamil Nadu, there are 12 corporations, 124 Municipalities and 528 Town Panchayats. Nearly 13968 tons solid wastes are generated per day and 12856 tons (92 %) are collected per day. In Madurai Corporation, nearly 450 MT solid wastes are generated per day and 185 MT wastes is land filled (1). Among the total waste generated nearly 29 % (w/w) vegetables and fruits waste in Madurai Corporation. At present Madurai Corporation is not practicing any safe or scientific solid waste disposal methods. The sources of fruit wastes are markets, domestic wastes, juice corners and food processing industries (2). Among the markets available in Tamil Nadu, major proportion is occupied by Farmers Market, popularly known as *Uzhavar Santhai*. At present 103 *Uzhavar Santhais* are functioning in Tamil Nadu and 26 *Uzhavar Santhais* are in Madurai Corporation.

Methods: Pectin was extracted by solvent extraction method and ethanol was extracted by fermentation with yeast. The extracted ethanol was utilized to extract pectin where lot of ethanol was required. The purity of pectin extracted from mixed fruit waste was checked by using HPLC and by comparing it with commercially available pectin. The extracted ethanol is also pure based on its melting point.

Results & Discussions: From the feasibility study there are 12 fruit vendors in *Uzhavar Santhai*, Chokkikulam and 65% of the vendors threw the fruits waste near the road side. On an average, 10 kg of fruits turned out as waste per vendor. So in total 120 kg of fruits waste was generated from one *Uzhavar Santhai*. In Madurai corporation 3120 kg of fruits waste is generating every day. In Tamil Nadu on an average 12360 kg of fruit waste is expected to generate. The prepared pectin has good food quality as prescribed by FCC. For mixture of fruits the amount of pectin formed was 4.3 g in 50 g of fruit peels.

Conclusions: Farmers can effectively use the process of pectin extraction for cottage industrial production as the procedure is simple and economically feasible. Collaboration can be made between Madurai Corporation and food industries to promote the utilization of extracted pectin in the production of various food products. The solid mass left after the extraction of pectin can be used as an adsorbent for various industrial effluents and also as fertilizers.

Keywords: *Pectin, Solid waste, Fruit waste, Ethanol.*

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